

Impact of Adopting eco-agricultural Conservation Practices on Farm Productivity and Commercialization in Ethiopia

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Abstract

The agricultural sector continues to be the main driver of economic growth in Ethiopia. In recent decades, the Ethiopian agricultural sector has faced several challenges, including subsistence farming, land fragmentation, poor technology adoption, low productivity, and ecosystem and land degradation. To reverse these challenges and their consequences, the attention of governments, researchers, and other stakeholders has recently shifted to the investigation and promotion of eco-agricultural conservation techniques that are assumed to simultaneously advance sustainable development, environmental enhancements, and economic growth. Hence, this study examines the impact of eco-agricultural conservation practices (organic fertilizer, crop rotation, and conservation tillage) on farm productivity and commercialization of smallholder vegetable producers in East Hararghe, Oromia, Ethiopia. A multistage sampling method was used to randomly select 383 households from three districts and nine kebeles from the East Hararghe zone. Questionnaires, focus group discussions, and key informant interviews were used to collect data. The collected data were analyzed using statistical tools, such as mean, chi-square, t-test for description and comparisons, and an econometric model called multinomial endogenous switching regression to estimate the impact of ECoPs. The results of the multinomial endogenous switching regression model revealed that adoption of ECoPs enhances farm productivity and the level of commercialization both solely and jointly, except for the joint adoption of conservation tillage and organic fertilizer. This confirms that joint adoption of various eco-agricultural conservation practices guarantees better results. Hence, due emphasis should be placed on promoting the adoption of ECoPs, and farmers should be cautious when adopting ECoPs.

Keywords: adoption, eco-agricultural conservation practices, Ethiopia, Multinomial endogenous switching regression, Productivity.

1. Introduction

In the past two decades, Ethiopia has highly stressed the expansion of small-scale irrigation to ensure the transformation of agriculture from subsistence farming to the commercialization of small-scale farmers. Vegetable production has become a renowned sector in Ethiopian agriculture, which has increased the commercialization of farm products. Vegetables account for approximately 18% of the total national agricultural sector production (CSA, 2014). Nevertheless, the actual vegetable production in this area is still below expectations owing to insufficient awareness of better production systems (Rahiel et al., 2018) agronomic and environmental factors (Gelmesa, 2018), and institutional and marketing challenges (Abeyou et al., 2019). The adoption of improved agricultural technologies has reinforced production enhancement in some countries (Evenson and Gollin, 2003), but has been less effective in Eastern Africa, including Ethiopia (Menale et al., 2015). Bezu et al. (2014) suggested that increased input use or intensification does not guarantee a corresponding increase in yields.

Moreover, numerous agricultural practices intended to maximize agricultural productivity cause environmental degradation and contribute to global warming and water pollution (Kim et al., 2016). In this arena, the significance of eco-agricultural conservation practices has become widely accepted, as they are the only systematic way to generate desired yields and achieve maximum economic and ecological outcomes instantaneously to lay a foundation for durable agricultural development and welfare (Pretty et al., 2011; Rogers et al., 2013). Hobbs and Gupta (2003) stated that conservation practices in the form of reduced tillage, zero tillage, and bed planting not only improve input use efficiency and minimize farming expenses, but also enhance the well-being of farmers, ensure biodiversity and ecosystem conservation, and provide plentiful environmental welfare.

Li et al. (2010) also pointed out that eco-agricultural conservation practices play a multidimensional role in reducing the negative impact of agriculture on the environment based on the practical realization of agricultural production functions, that is, by coordinating the social and economic benefits of agricultural production with ecological and environmental benefits.

Consequently, eco-agricultural conservation practices (ECoPs) are expected to ensure the double-edged benefits of economic development and environmental protection by conserving soil fertility, reducing deforestation, and producing greater production in existing production areas with the lowest environmental pressure (Nkomoki et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2019).

In East Hararghe, several studies on adoption have mostly focused on the adoption of technologies (Mengistu and Degefu, 2017) and practices that enhance yield through intensification. Unfortunately, the drawbacks of these technologies, such as land degradation, soil acidification, pesticide residues, and reduced biodiversity, have received no attention (He et al., 2016)

Studies have shown that the adoption of eco-agricultural conservation practices contributes to improvements in the environmental carrying capacity and system stability (He et al., 2016). Hence, the adoption of eco-agricultural conservation practices is considered a fundamental approach to ameliorate the problems of low productivity and the level of commercialization of smallholder farmers (Godfray and Garnett, 2014). Asfaw et al. (2012) contributed to discovering an existing relationship between the adoption of sustainable eco-agricultural technologies and the commercialization of smallholder farmers via productivity. Gadanakis (2014) studied the impact of ecological conservation practices on productivity. However, these studies are insufficient to gain a better understanding of sustainable production and marketing systems.

In addition, such studies failed to recognize that merely increasing production without having enough market linkages will not ensure smallholders' welfare (Tesfay, 2020). Therefore, this study intends to fill the prevailing knowledge gaps by investigating the adoption impacts of eco-agricultural conservation practices on farm productivity and commercialization. The selected eco-agricultural conservation practices were crop rotation, organic fertilizer application, and conservation tillage.

In this specific context, the study's objective was

- 1) To estimate the impact of adopting eco-agricultural conservation practices on farm productivity and the level of commercialization among smallholder vegetable producers.

The impact of ECoPs on farm productivity may vary and can be influenced by land features, types of cultivated crops, characteristics of farmers, types of ECoPs to be adopted, and other factors. As a result, the data and information generated from this study can help the government and other stakeholders as evidence for evaluations of ECoPs on farm productivity. An understanding of the impact of ECoPs on smallholders' commercialization level will generate information that supports comprehensive policy decisions to improve the efficacy of adopting ECoPs in the realization of the projected increase in commercial levels of agricultural production.

1.2. Definitions and operationalization of key terms

This sub-section presents some basic definitions of the key terms used in this study.

Adoption: Although word adoption is one of the most challenging terms not only to define (CIMMYT, 1993) but also to measure (Erenstein et al., 2012), various scholars have defined it differently. Rogers (1983) and Feder et al. (1985) define adoption as the choice made by economic units to regularly apply new techniques, procedures, and technologies. It is the knowledge or information that allows some services to be rendered or tasks to be undertaken in a simpler and better way (Lavison, 2013). According to Feder et al. (1985), technology is adopted only when it is applied uninterruptedly in the farmers' fields and entirely assimilated into the family's agricultural system. Hence, this study considers the operational definition provided by Feder et al. (1985).

Eco-agricultural conservation practice: The term eco-agriculture is defined by McNeely and Scherr (2001) as "landscapes that achieve the joint objectives of sustainable agricultural production, biodiversity and ecosystem conservation, and rural livelihoods". Hence, in this study, eco-agricultural conservation practices are operationalized as farming practices that realize the mutual goals of sustainable economic, ecological, environmental, and agricultural productivity, biodiversity, and ecosystem conservation.

Farm Productivity: The primary definition of productivity for over 200 years has been output divided by input. According to Fulginiti and Perrin (1998), agricultural productivity is the amount of agricultural output produced by a given farm using a given level of input(s). More

precisely, this study followed and operationalized the definition given by Olayide and Heady (1982), and calculated farm productivity as the ratio of the value of total farm outputs to the total amount of inputs utilized in agricultural production.

Commercialization: This is described as the complete set of steps necessary to guarantee the readiness of a product for sale. Pingali (1997) defined agricultural commercialization as the choice made by farmers regarding product choice and input usage and is based on the principles of profit maximization.

2. Methodology

2.1. Description of the Study Area

This study was conducted in the eastern Oromia Regional State of Ethiopia. Oromia. The East Hararghe Zone is geographically located between 7°32'-9°44' north latitude and 41°10'-43°16' east longitude, with altitudes ranging from 500 to 3405 m above sea level (PEDO, 1997). The East Hararghe Zone is well known for its vegetable production. According to CSA (2021), the total area allocated for vegetable cultivation in East Hararghe is estimated as 544.30 ha and generated nearly about 33,175.33 quintals of vegetables. This zone has 18 administrative districts.

2.2. Sampling Technique

This study employed a multi-stage sampling technique to select the required sample. Initially, purposive sampling was used to purposively select three districts from the 19 districts of the East Hararghe Zone, considering their potential for vegetable production capability and participation in adopting eco-agricultural conservation practices related to the remaining districts of the zone. Second, we used stratified random sampling to stratify the list of kebeles into vegetable and non-vegetable producers. Third, using a simple random sampling method, three vegetable producer kebeles were selected from every *Woreda* (district) proportional to size. Finally, the total sample size (383 households) was obtained using Kothari's (2004) formula:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 pq N}{e^2(N-1) + Z^2 pq} = \frac{(1.96)^2(0.5)(0.5)(89215)}{(0.05)^2(89214) + (1.96)^2(0.5)(0.5)} = 382.51 \approx 383$$

2.3. Data types and Data Collection Techniques

This study gathered both the primary and secondary data. Secondary data were collected from government organizations, such as the East Hararghe zone agricultural office, woreda agricultural offices, reports and documents of sampled kebeles, and non-government organizations. Primary data were gathered from adopters and non-adopters of ECoPs in vegetable-producer households. Several data collection methods, namely questionnaires, key informant interviews, focus group discussions, and field observations, were employed. Data were collected from the study area during the 2021/22 production year.

3. Data Analysis Methods

Several alternative econometric models have been employed by various scholars to conduct impact studies. Among these models, the most widely used are the; difference-in-difference, instrumental variable method, propensity score matching, generalized propensity score matching, switching regression, and randomized selection methods.

The difference-in-difference model helps compare the treatment and control groups before (no project) and after project implementation. It is very helpful and applicable only when the baseline and time-series data of both the treatment and control groups are accessible (Stern *et al.*, 2012). The instrumental variables approach is also an alternative model for impact studies. It uses instruments to handle confounding factors and measurement errors. Its drawback is that; if the instruments are weak, confounders increase the standard errors. This, in turn, leads to inaccurate and biased results. It also suggests the inclusion of at least one variable, Z , which is an instrument that helps describe treatment status (Abadie, 2003; Heckman and Vytlačil, 2005). Propensity score matching is a statistical matching approach used in the comparison of two subject groups (Rubin, 2001). It is applied to evaluate a project's impact by comparing beneficiaries with non-beneficiaries with similar propensity scores. Its limitation is that PSM entails a large sample size, as it eliminates some participants who are not matched, which in turn leads to incomplete matching. Incomplete matching may affect the generalizability of the results

OLS estimates of (1) are inconsistent and thus, require correction. Hence, to estimate the parameter β_r , consistently, opting for the selection process is of paramount importance. This is why; we must select the other choices within the ECoPs.

Consequently, we incorporated the selection correction terms derived from equation (1) and postulated a multinomial endogenous switching model (selection bias-corrected outcome equation following Bourguignon *et al.* (2007) as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \text{Regime1: } Y_{i1} = X_{i1}\beta_1 + \sigma_1\hat{\lambda}_{i1} + \varphi_{i1} \text{ if } I = 1 \\ \vdots \\ \text{RegimeR: } Y_{ir} = X_{ir}\beta_r + \sigma_r\hat{\lambda}_{ir} + \varphi_{ir} \text{ if } I = R \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

σ_r displays how much μ 's and ϵ 's vary together, i.e., covariance while the λ_r is a ratio of the probability density function to the cumulative distribution function of the Inverse Mills Ratio (IMR). This study employed the full information maximum likelihood estimation (Lokshin & Sajaia, 2004) to assess the endogenous switching regression models. After estimating the model's parameters, estimating the average treatment effect on the treated (ATT) by comparing the expected values of outcomes of adopters and non-adopters of ECoPs in actual and counterfactual scenarios will be figured as follows:

$$\text{Adopters with adoption (actual): } \begin{cases} E(Y_{i2}|I = 2) = X_i\beta_2 + \sigma_2\hat{\lambda}_2 \\ \vdots \\ E(Y_{i2}|I = R) = X_i\beta_R + \sigma_R\hat{\lambda}_2 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Farmers adopting ECoPs, had they chosen not to adopt (Counterfactual):

$$\begin{cases} E(Y_{i1}|I = 2) = X_i\beta_1 + \sigma_1\hat{\lambda}_2 \\ \vdots \\ E(Y_{i1}|I = R) = X_i\beta_R + \sigma_R\hat{\lambda}_R \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Equations (3) and (4) are used to measure the ATT, which is derived as the difference between the actual and counterfactual expected values and written as:

$$ATT = E[Y_{i2}|I = 2] - E[Y_{i1}|I = 2] = X_i(\beta_2 - \beta_1) + \lambda_2(\sigma_2 - \sigma_1) \quad (5)$$

Here, the right-hand-side of equation (5) designates the probability of the change in the adopter's explained variables when adopters have similar behaviours as non-adopters. The λ_i is

the term that stands for selection by catching all probable results raised from unobservable random variables. It is worth noticing that the overall fitness of the endogenous switching regression model was checked from the likelihood ratio test statistics to be displayed together with the model results. Tests for endogeneity and over identification restrictions were conducted using Durbin and Sargan test. Heteroskedasticity was controlled with the use of a robust standard error estimation based on White (1982).

4. Results and Discussion

This section presents the impact of ECoPs on farm productivity and commercialization. This can be obtained from the estimated average treatment effects of adopting various combinations of ECoPs on the outcome variable under both actual and counterfactual cases, as shown in table 1. As shown in table 1, the results underscored that adopters of ECoPs produce more yield than non-adopters. Additionally, the results also generated other important points: although joint adoption of ECoPs is better for farmers in terms of generating better yields, not all combinations of ECoPs are useful. Among the four alternative combinations, the results revealed that farmers that jointly adopted organic fertilizer with crop rotation ($T_0C_1O_1$) produced the highest production (52.69 qt). This indicates that these two practices have complementarities or that there is a positive interaction between them. This result was congruent with the study undertaken by Shibabaw *et al.* (2018), who estimated the joint adoption effect of organic fertilizer and crop rotation on potato productivity, showing that the amalgamation of these two technologies is environmentally sound and enhances output.

The results also showed that among the farmers who adopted only a single practice, those adopting exclusively organic fertilizer ($T_0C_0O_1$) attained a higher yield than the other two practices. According to the results of this study, even the adoption of organic fertilizer is better than the joint adoption of conservation tillage and organic fertilizer ($T_1C_0O_1$). This result proves that farmers generate nothing by adopting these two practices together. This result indicates that these practices are substitutable; that is, farmers can adopt either of these practices to realize targeted farm yield. It is also worth noting that conservation tillage as a package may involve minimum tillage or no tillage, whereas the application of organic fertilizer requires additional farm activities that may prevent the adoption of no-tillage. Based on this result, it can be

interpreted that farmers can adopt both practices interchangeably and inversely; their joint adoption at one time may harm productivity and hence lead to over-exploitation of unnecessary resources.

Concerning the percentage impact of ECoPs on the productivity level of farm products of smallholders, the results in Table 1 show that regarding the particular adoption of certain practices, adoption of conservation tillage revealed the lowest impact percentage of 9.91%, and the highest impact (30.9) was achieved by smallholder farmers who adopted crop rotation. Regarding the percentage impact of the joint adoption of ECoPs on farm productivity, the highest impact (36.46%) was obtained from the combined adoption of crop rotation and organic fertilizer ($T_0C_1O_1$).

Table 1. MESR-based result of average treatment effect of adoption of ECoPs on farm productivity.

Explained variable	Decision	Adoption status		Treatment effect	% of impact
		Adopter i=2,3,4,5,6,7	Non-adopter i=1		
		1	2	3=1-2	4=(3 ÷ 2) x100
Farm productivity(in Qt)	$T_1C_0O_0$	34.14 (0.75)	31.06 (0.82)	3.08*** (1.18)	9.91
	$T_0C_1O_0$	44.83 (2.42)	34.27 (1.91)	10.59*** (3.90)	30.90
	$T_0C_0O_1$	46.11 (2.79)	40.97 (2.18)	5.13*** (3.50)	12.52
	$T_1C_1O_0$	48.39	40.12	7.99***	19.91

	(3.17)	(1.91)	(3.51)	
T ₁ C ₀ O ₁	41.23 (3.73)	41.70 (2.50)	-0.47 (4.60)	-1.12
T ₀ C ₁ O ₁	52.59 (2.44)	38.61 (2.08)	14.08*** (3.21)	36.46
T ₁ C ₁ O ₁	39.63 (2.17)	47.27 (3.85)	-7.64 (4.91)	-16.16

Source: Calculated from survey (2022). “i” symbolizes adoption combinations of ECoPs, *** and ** shows significance at 1% and 5% respectively.

Concerning the percentage impact of ECoPs on the productivity level of farm products of smallholders, the results in Table 2 show that regarding the particular adoption of certain practices, adoption of conservation tillage revealed the lowest impact percentage that was 9.91%, and the highest impact (30.9) was achieved by smallholder farmer who adopted crop rotation. Regarding the percentage impact of the joint adoption of ECoPs on farm productivity, the highest impact (36.46%) was obtained from the combined adoption of crop rotation and organic fertilizer (T₀C₁O₁).

Regarding the impact of ECoPs on commercialization, the result generated from the multinomial endogenous switching regression-based average treatment effect of adoption showed that adoption of ECoPs had a positive and significant effect on enhancing the level of commercialization among smallholder vegetable producers. Nevertheless, ECoPs did not have the same percentage influence on the level of commercialization as they did on farm production.

The possible justification behind this may be the small farm size and inadequacy of the land in the study area, which locked farmers’ potential from increasing the commercialization of agricultural products. The average effect estimation revealed that the maximum calculation impact of ECoPs on commercialization was 13 percent. As shown in the table below, ECoPs had a positive influence on commercialization at the single and joint levels.

Considering the adoption of single practices, individuals who adopted only crop rotation ($T_0C_1O_0$) showed an approximately 13 percent improvement in commercializing farm products. Farmers may find crop rotation beneficial in terms of preserving soil resources that would otherwise be depleted by monoculture or specialization, and provide several products to the market by adopting crop rotation. At the joint level, the result showed that farmers who jointly adopted organic fertilizer and crop rotation recorded extra seven percent enhancements in the level of commercialization. However, the adoption of conservation tillage with crop rotation ($T_1C_1O_0$) showed no significant impact on the farmers' level of commercialization. The probable insight obtained from this result is that farmers who adopt these practices conjointly are inclined to environmental aspects rather than commercialization, as these practices improve environmental performance more than other things.

It is worth remarking that in multinomial endogenous regression, base heterogeneity helps compare the impact of adopting eco-agricultural conservation practices (ECoPs) on adopters' and non-adopters' households. There were two types of base heterogeneity. These are called the base heterogeneities for adopters and non-adopters. The adopter's base heterogeneity is computed as the difference between the adopter's outcome (farm productivity and commercialization) and the non-adopter's outcome (farm productivity and commercialization); if they had adopted ECoPs.

The difference between farm productivity and commercialization of adopter households if they had not adopted, and the farm productivity and commercialization of non-adopter households is the base heterogeneity for non-adopters. The manifestation of particular heterogeneity, when adopters and non-adopters have similar adoption status, is displayed by the negative sign of the base heterogeneity of non-adopters.

Table 2. MESR-based average treatment effect of adoption of ECoPs on farm commercialization

Outcome variable	Decision	Adoption status		Treatment effect	% of impact effect
		Adopter i=2,3,4,5,6,7	Non-adopter i=1		
		1	2	3=1-2	4=(3 ÷ 2) x100
Commercialization (commercialization index)	T ₁ C ₀ O ₀	0.77 (0.01)	0.69 (0.02)	0.07*** (0.02)	10.14
	T ₀ C ₁ O ₀	0.82 (0.01)	0.72 (0.02)	0.10*** (0.02)	13.88
	T ₀ C ₀ O ₁	0.86 (0.01)	0.84 (0.01)	0.02** (0.02)	2.3
	T ₁ C ₁ O ₀	0.87 (0.02)	0.86 (0.03)	0.01 (0.04)	1.16
	T ₁ C ₀ O ₁	0.79 (0.03)	0.79 (0.01)	0.001*** (0.03)	0.12
	T ₀ C ₁ O ₁	0.89 (0.01)	0.83 (0.01)	0.06*** (0.02)	7.22
	T ₁ C ₁ O ₁	0.80 (0.01)	0.93 (0.05)	-0.13 (0.06)	-13.97

Source: Own survey (2022). N.B.: “i” represents adoption combinations of ECoPs, *** and ** shows significance at 1% and 5% correspondingly.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

This study aimed to disclose the ECoPs nexus between farm productivity and commercialization. To this end, multinomial endogenous switching regression was employed to estimate the impact of ECoPs on farm productivity and the level of commercialization of farmers. The results of the model showed inconsistent effects of adoption of ECoPs on productivity and the commercial level of the farmer₂, where the combination of conservation tillage and organic fertilizer had negative effects on farm productivity₂ and joint adoption of crop rotation and organic fertilizer also showed no effect on the level of commercialization of the farmers. Concerning the impact of the adoption of ECoPs on farm productivity and commercialization, since this study approved the positive adoption effects of ECoPs on productivity and commercialization, policies that promote the adoption of ECoPs should have come into effect. Given this, some of the joint adoption of ECoPs was confirmed to have no effect or even a negative effect on productivity and commercialization. This might call for additional investigations to judge the impact of the studied and other remaining impacts of ECoPs on the productivity and commercialization of smallholder vegetable producers.

Declarations

Funding statement

This research did not receive any specific grants from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Data availability statement

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author [upon](#) reasonable request.

Declaration of interests' statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Additional information

No additional information is available for this paper.

Ethical Approval

Approval to conduct research and collect data from respondents was obtained from Haramaya University's postgraduate directorate (research permit number HUSP-2022-8095). Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, and the study contained no experiment on humans and/or the use of human or animal tissue samples.

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